

What motivates authoritarian regimes to adopt free trade policies? A single case study of Vietnam and the role of trust in domestic political institutions

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Abstract

After the Cold War, free trade spread rapidly, driven by the Washington Consensus and the Soviet Union's collapse. Many assumed this would promote democracy and unify global values, shaping international relations for decades. Yet, democracy is declining while authoritarian regimes increasingly adopt free trade policies. This study explores why these regimes embrace international trade, focusing on Vietnam, and tests whether greater public trust in institutions boosts free trade adoption. It does not evaluate the quality of regimes or their institutions.

Keywords: trade, reform, trust, Vietnam, economic liberalization, authoritarianism

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Introduction

For decades, globalization and the liberal international order grew hand in hand. Lately, though, forces resisting globalization have gained strength, straining that order (Kornprobst et al., 2021). So, what is next? One possibility is ‘deglobalization,’ where global trade and cross-border investment drop. Another is a world split into rival economic blocs, reshaping trade ties rather than breaking them (Shearing, 2023). Either way, global GDP might hold steady in the coming years instead of falling, despite forecasts tied to deglobalization’s effects.

The International Monetary Fund (IMF) recently issued its gloomiest outlook in 50 years, predicting global economic growth of 2.8% in 2023 and 3% over the next five years. This slowdown signals globalization unraveling, shaped by geography and population trends. Low growth seems unavoidable now, hinting at rising geopolitical tensions. This comes after a striking post-pandemic spike in global demand (BIS, 2023:24), even as trade growth has stalled since 2008 (Figure 1) amid supply chain struggles.

Figure 1: As a proportion of world GDP, trade growth has deteriorated since 2008

Ratio of the world GDP to world goods exports, both in constant prices at Q1 2000 USD. Annual world GDP data backdated and interpolated to quarterly frequency using a constructed quarterly world GDP aggregate for a smaller sample of economies (due to data constraints). Annual world goods exports volume data interpolated to quarterly frequency using world goods exports value data (due to data constraints). Based on Chow-Lin method for temporal disaggregation.

Sources: Jordà-Schularick-Taylor Macrohistory Database; IMF; World Bank; WTO; Global Financial Data; national data; BIS.

Inflation returned and monetary policy had to be tightened, pressuring governmental finances and private-sector balance sheets, exposing a decline of public trust in the fairness and capabilities of democratic governments to provide material goods and a sense of fulfilment throughout developed economies (WVS, 2022). Additionally, the Economist Intelligence Unit (EIU) (2023) has shown a global decline in democracy between 2016 and 2022.

In the case of trade policy, interactions between economics and politics are more complex than other fields. Public opinion does matter. When enough people are convinced that a policy is wrong, politicians are less likely to support it. And the emerging challenges of democratic legitimacy has shown new tensions regarding regime type and international trade.

Particularly, the importance of international status has been revalidated as a geopolitical strain. The ratio of world goods exports to GDP has reverted to the levels seen in 2000. This trend can be interpreted not merely as a slowdown in globalization, but rather a gradual process of deglobalization. Shin (2017, 2023) highlights that the world economy has been a mosaic and is likely to remain so (Figure 2), which helps to understand the contestation of globalization in the international society, as it is composed by networks that link specific nodes. He proposes that globalization has never been characterized by universal trade or financial flows between all entities. Different sectors operate according to distinct logics and regions of the world.

Figure 2: Global Supply Chain Networks by sector, industry, and country (Shin, 2023)

The recent slowdown in worldwide trade and foreign direct investment (FDI) has been driven by the rivalry between China and the United States (US). This competitive dynamic is encouraging both countries to gradually disengage from each other, a move not just observed in their trade and FDI relations, but most significantly, in their technological interactions. This geopolitical tension is congruent with the idea of industrial nodes if we account global value chains and delocalization. Similarly, distance emerges as a relevant variable as an OECD report (Guillemette and Turner, 2018) acknowledges the geopolitical shift towards the Pacific to become the main global hub of trade and growth. The distance from relevant Asia-Pacific actors will affect the relative position of countries in the world economy (Figure 3).

Figure 3: Change in remoteness from main trade hub by 2060 in the baseline scenario (OECD, 2018)

The rapid economic regionalization in East Asia allowed governments to negotiate the terms of their economic internationalization, accommodating a diverse set of political systems. The region’s fastest growth rate in the last two decades was achieved in authoritarian Vietnam, only

affected by the economic impact of COVID19 (Figure 4). Felker (2018) explains that this is a good example on how Southeast Asia’s interventionist polities had successfully adapted their ‘managed globalization’ strategies to the regional and global political economy.

Figure 4: Vietnam GDP growth (annual %) (World Bank, 2023)

When authoritarian countries can choose the degree to which they want to be part of the world, it is likely that the adoption of free-market economic structures for purposes unaligned with liberal principles will be commonplace. A plausible scenario embodies aspects of economic liberalism which are most appealing to authoritarian leaders and populist politicians, and those that ‘equip major and regional powers with resources to seek global influence’ (Cooley and Nexon, 2021). Originally, East Asian authoritarian governments associated with the communist economic model emphasized the collective ownership of all the means of production of the national economy, generating the dichotomy (Figure 5) between socialist and capitalist systems.

Figure 5: Model of socialist and capitalist systems (Sahut and Teulon, 2021)

Nonetheless, the region experienced what Fritzen (2018) calls ambiguous -authoritarian-decentralization in Thailand, Cambodia, and Vietnam. These countries undertook intricate

reforms to restructure the financial and administrative connections between central and local governments. They aim to utilize decentralization to boost administrative efficiency and augment public legitimacy. However, consolidating the control of central authorities over local governments.

These reforms have made the socialist-capitalist system outdated to properly understand the dynamics of the region. Whereas trust appears as a factor that can potentially impact economic performance via microeconomic and macropolitical pathways. Knack (2001) argues that on the micro scale, social relationships and interpersonal trust can lessen transaction costs, enforce contracts, and ease credit access for individual investors. On the macro scale, the social unity that underpins trust could enhance democratic governance, augment the efficiency and integrity of public administration, and enhance the impact of economic policies.

Global economic integration became a prominent topic of public interest, across developed and developing nations. Therefore, we need deeper and varied perspectives to understand its relationship with public trust. We also need a more detailed theoretical framework that aims to explore the roots of differing public views on preferential trade liberalization. Kiratli (2020) argues that this exercise would be beneficial for policymakers, who could use this information to either choose their trade partners more strategically or frame trade liberalization with proposed partners in a way that garners stronger support from the electorate.

The current global geopolitical situation underlines the relevance of understanding authoritarian regimes as the emerging actors of global trade, including the elements that influence public sensitivity in selecting trade partners, and how the narrative is conducted to legitimize the implementation of free trade policy.

Literature review

Scholars have widely studied how trust in domestic institutions shapes preferences for international trade. Defining political regimes, however, remains challenging due to tensions within political science traditions (Figure 6) that complicate regime classification. Przeworski (2022) notes that authoritarian governments are often viewed negatively, yet their routine operations—like fixing potholes—suggest many actions aren’t solely about retaining power. He adds that ordinary people rarely obsess over politics in any system. Coppedge (2011) also argues that indices measuring regime types, typically focused on democracy, have limits and rarely yield perfectly positive or negative scores.

Figure 6: Existing Data Sets on Democracy: An Evaluation (Munck and Verkuilen, 2002)

Name	Strengths	Weaknesses
ACLP: Alvarez, Cheibub, Limongi, & Przeworski	Identification of attributes: offices Conceptual logic Appropriate selection of indicators Clear and detailed coding rules	Minimalist definition: omission of participation and agenda setting
Arat	Identification of attributes: offices and agenda setting	Conceptual logic: problem of conflation
Bollen	Identification of attributes: offices, agenda setting, and fairness	Minimalist definition: omission of participation Conceptual logic: problem of conflation Restricted empirical (temporal) scope
Coppedge & Reinicke Polyarchy	Identification of attributes: fairness Test of intercoder reliability Sophisticated aggregation procedure	Minimalist definition: omission of participation, offices, and agenda setting Restricted empirical (temporal) scope
Freedom House	Comprehensive empirical (spatial) scope	Maximalist definition Conceptual logic: problem of conflation Multiple problems of measurement Inappropriate aggregation procedure
Gasiorowski Political Regime Change	Comprehensive empirical scope	Minimalist definition: omission of offices and agenda setting Multiple problems of measurement
Hadenius	Identification of attributes: offices, agenda setting, and fairness Appropriate selection of indicators Clear and detailed coding rules Sophisticated aggregation procedure	Conceptual logic: problems of redundancy and conflation Restricted empirical (temporal) scope
Polity IV	Identification of attributes: offices and agenda setting Clear and detailed coding rules Test of intercoder reliability Comprehensive empirical scope	Minimalist definition: omission of participation Conceptual logic: problem of redundancy Inappropriate aggregation procedure
Vanhanen	Clear coding rules Comprehensive empirical scope Replicability	Minimalist definition: omission of offices and agenda setting Questionable indicators Inappropriate aggregation procedure

Welzel (2020) offers a useful framework for this study. He argues that people’s life outlooks shape their cultural values and, in turn, the regimes they support. Those focused on prevention embrace patriarchal values—authority, favouritism, and insider networks—while those geared toward promotion prefer emancipative ideals like liberty, fairness, and clear agreements. In his view, patriarchal values prop up autocratic systems, while emancipative ones back democratic ones (Figure 7).

Figure 7: Welzel's framework of cultural regimes (Welzel, 2020)

Consequently, the role of Confucian-Buddhism as a provider of 'structural and institutional support for the formation of state and society' for the Vietnamese political order identified by Huang (2022b) and defined by its 'centralized, hierarchic authority relations in the polity, literate class, government bureaucrats, and the royal house' appears consistent. Also, facilitates the segmentation of regime types in East Asia through type of authority, similarly as previous examples with Asian democracies in 2004 (Figure 8).

Figure 8: Political Regimes in Asia (Aurel Croissant, 2004)

	South Asia	South-east Asia	North-east Asia
Electoral democracies (second wave)	Sri Lanka, India	—	Japan
Electoral democracies (third wave)	Bangladesh	Indonesia, Philippines, Thailand	South Korea, Taiwan
Failed democracies	Nepal (democracy suspended, October 2002), Pakistan (coup d'etat, October 1999)	Cambodia (putsch, July 1997)	—
Autocratic regimes	Bhutan, Maldives	Brunei, Laos, Malaysia, Myanmar, Singapore, Vietnam	China, North Korea

Sources: Classifications by the author based on information from Freedom House, *Freedom in the World. The Annual Survey of Political Rights and Civil Liberties, 2001–02* (New York: Freedom House, 2002); *Nepal Research* (<http://nepalresearch.org/politics/>, accessed 10 April 2003).

Regardless of the region, global authoritarianism is on the rise (Acemoglu, 2023). Which complemented with the global rise on demand and trade, underlines the need of 'better understanding of global trends of democratization and autocratization. (Boese 2021)', because the abundance of studies focused on democracy has left the field lacking on reliable tools to work with this trend.

Southeast Asian studies is another contested field. Pepinsky (2014) describes this tension as the lack of agreement on the meaning of context between area studies and comparative politics. He concludes that population context (the one preferred by comparative politics) is the superior approach. Since his work focuses on the populations' trust in its government, his approach seems adequate to steer our methodological efforts. The subregion relevance increased after China and Vietnam became the global fastest expanding economies of the last two decades. Nonetheless, Malesky (2011, 2021) compares the polities of both countries and found that Vietnamese elites 'encourage the construction of broader policy-making coalitions, have more competitive selection processes, and place more constraints on executive decision-making' than China. Another relevant work on the region belongs to Morgenbesser (2020) who built a framework and dataset to measure and classify Southeast Asian autocracies. His innovative input recognizes that these regimes can hold periodical elections and implement liberal trade policies as sophisticated authoritarianisms to remain sustainable. Similarly, the findings of Slater and Wong (2013, 2022) describe Asian democratic reforms by autocratic regimes as a 'proactive strategy to revitalize their power from a position of strength', although for the case of Vietnam they define the reforms as intractable.

The 2000s witnessed a wide interest on the diffusion of liberalization at a national level, although most of them focused on democracy. However, the work by Simmons et. al. (2008) on how policy and political change can adequately be understood by conceiving national governments as independent decision makers and focusing on explanations 'based on the specific conditions governments encounter'. By dividing liberalism on its economic variant as that result in marketization (Figure 9a) and its political variant that results in democratization (Figure 9b).

Figure 9a and 9b: Variation in liberalization and democratization (Simmons et. al., 2008)

These distinctions on liberalism are key to comprehend the advent of the new 'socialist consumer classes' described by Hansen (2017), as the political-economic contexts that foster them are no longer limited by the democratic-autocratic spectrum. They can steer the 'consumption patterns and consumer culture' towards the benefit of the regime.

Research on why authoritarian states engage in processes of marketization remains scarce. Extensive work by Milner and Kubota (2005) implies the necessity to extend academic analysis as 'the impact of different political institutions on trade policy is an unexplored area of great potential interest. Similarly, Viatkin and Komarova (2014) explore why autocracies use neoliberal governance techniques. Since control of the public sector is essential for authoritarian regimes, they argue that 'governments must have compelling reasons to opt for its neoliberalization'. Additionally, Kim and Heio (2018) question the premise of economic globalization advancing democratization through economic development by the lack of reform

in the political systems of Vietnam and Laos. Arguing that there is an indirect link to political changes, that should be accounted for.

While literature on trade policy preferences is mainly focused on how trade's re-distributional implications affect people's attitudes on the problem, recent research is particularly interested in investigating the role of non-economic variables. As seen in the extensive analysis of the Eurobarometer survey by Braml and Felbermayr (2020) where 'individual preferences for open-market policies are mainly shaped by trust in institutions and not economic self-interest'. Coincidentally, Rho and Thomz (2017) evidence that 'when it comes to trade, most people do not exhibit the sophisticated beliefs and egoistic preferences we would expect if each were maximizing their own material interests according to economic theory', then, why are people interested in the promotion of free trade among their countries? Maybe understood as trust might provide a solid starting point.

There is an extensive body of work on trust, but it often leads to more ambiguity than clarity. How do individuals develop trust in their government? A rational perspective on trust is the most common, anchored on perceptions of the delivery of public services. The prevailing argument is that when individuals believe the government acts in their favour, this positive experience forms social trust. Putnam's (1995, 1999, 2001) influential social capital theory argues how civic participation fosters social trust, subsequently enhancing governmental effectiveness. Yet, overlooks social trust as a foundation for trusting the government. Whilst Job (2005) finds that even if civic engagement plays a role creating social trust, the central driver of trust in government is relational i.e.: based on our intimate experiences. Concluding that 'relational factors co-exist in creating trust in government and its organisations'.

Nguyen and Bernauer (2018) focus on the drivers of trust. They explain that 'Trust in specific types of actors such as policy makers or economic institutions is likely to be relevant for public support for trade policy as well.' but argue in favour of the positive effect that generalized social trust can have in the support for free trade. Comparable to the findings of Kaltenthaler and Miller (2014) who 'contend that the level of social trust an individual has will condition the degree to which an individual wants to open her country to imports from other countries'.

Therefore, how should we measure trust in institutions? The most common methods are public opinion polls -barometers- which allow for cross-country comparisons. Their reliability lies in the fact that 'survey questions on trust are well understood by respondents and that findings from different opinion surveys are consistent with each other' (UN DESA, 2021). Understanding trust as a steering force of public opinion towards trade agreements, Butler, Giuliano, and Guiso (2016) discuss its influence on citizens' attitudes towards regional trade agreements; while Riley and Saavedra (2019) suggest that 'international trade does have a significant and relatively large positive effect on social trust'.

Overall, trust within autocracies remains understudied. A literature gap that hinders answers to this work's main question. Also, most studies are observational, which limits the likelihood of finding causal effects in the correlation between trade preferences and trust. However, the scholarly consensus is that trade policy preferences rely on how the issues are framed, while Jakobsen's (2010) focus shift focus from aggregated public opinion to individual trust on institutions, helps reduce methodological complexity. And the work by Nguyen (2019) on the role of social trust in shaping public support for international trade in Vietnam, identifies that higher levels of social trust are positively associated with increased support for international trade, providing a solid starting point for this analysis.

Background

Globalization, especially free trade, has sparked debate since emerging as a distinct field of study (Berezin, 2013). This debate grew sharper in the 21st century after China joined the WTO in 2001, the 2008 financial crisis hit, and the 2019 pandemic unfolded, prompting calls for a new globalization consensus. In the 1990s, many thought free trade would spread liberal and democratic values globally (Simmons, 2008; Gleditsch and Ward, 2006). Yet Freedom House (2023) reports more countries lost freedoms than gained them over the past 17 years—a trend possibly driving authoritarian shifts in nations like Brazil, Hungary, India, and the United States. Meanwhile, many authoritarian regimes adopt free trade policies without democratizing, paired with growing scepticism toward liberal trade systems.

Scholars of liberalism argue that globalization has scattered and loosened power networks. Farrell and Newman (2019) label this ‘weaponized interdependence,’ where states tap into trade and exchange networks for strategic edge. Middle and smaller powers exploit this, hinting at new geopolitical zones that defy old norms. Leaders no longer fixate on security alone, moving beyond theories like Realism, Contractualism, and Constructivism (Jackson, 2019). Instead, economic networks—think finance, supply chains, and the internet—blend with domestic systems to shape authority. This view highlights these networks as key to understanding globalization’s impact on power, with Buzan and Zhang’s (2014) regional focus aiding this study’s approach.

One overlooked element of networks is distance. The OECD recognizes the ‘distance effect’ as a relevant element to leverage in the coming years (Guillemette and Turner, 2018), and highly likely to set the pace on the geopolitical configuration of the Asia-Pacific region. Quah (2011) favours including ‘entire cross-country distribution of economic and political activity’ to improve our understanding of future dynamics of global inequality, regional power shifts, and trade, influencing works beyond academia, as can be seen in Figure 10.

Figure 10: Evolution of the earth's economic centre of gravity AD 1 to 2025

1 Economic center of gravity is calculated by weighting locations by GDP in three dimensions and projected to the nearest point on the earth's surface. The surface projection of the center of gravity shifts north over the course of the century, reflecting the fact that in three-dimensional space America and Asia are not only “next” to each other, but also “across” from each other.

SOURCE: McKinsey Global Institute analysis using data from Angus Maddison; University of Groningen

Evidence tends to support the claim to improve approaches and methods with contextual evidence. Findings in the extensive work of Goh (2007) showcase that for decades, Southeast Asian states have designed their national security strategies to steer clear of what they perceive as either Chinese or US ‘spheres of influence’. Arguably, the overarching regional context is

outlined by an ongoing geopolitical tension between China and the US, manufacture delocalization, and the convergence of global trade interests.

As relevant regional actors, Southeast Asian autocracies are choosing to implement trade and limited political reforms, subtly changing the traditional understanding on the nature of authoritarianism. The regional growth experience cannot be understood without recognizing the role of interventionist governments accelerating the pace (Beeson and Breslin, 2014:116). In the long term, these regimes face the challenge of implementing reforms that foster a stable financial and macroeconomic environment while strengthening the potential for robust and sustainable growth. On one hand, this approach would allow them to avoid domestic unrest, a critical factor in maintaining regime stability. On the other, steering individual preferences by building social trust could reduce risks associated with opening to international markets and their credibility.

This work explores the previously exposed dynamics to provide a nuanced understanding of free trade adoption by authoritarian regimes. Trust in domestic political institutions, in this case applied to the government and head of state, is proposed as a key factor influencing their adoption. So far, all the evidence agrees on the need to keep track on the nature and behaviour of current and future autocracies, considering their increasing protagonism.

Why the Focus on Authoritarian Regimes?

Over the past decades, a substantial body of work has been dedicated to examining the relationship between democratic political structures and trade policy outcomes. Although, it has largely neglected the policy-making practices among autocratic states. Even when authoritarian variation on national trade policies is generally recognized, as one would find it challenging to claim that North Korea has more open markets compared to China and Vietnam.

One proposition argues that authoritarian regimes with more established institutions are likely to embrace open trade policies. Hankla and Kuthy (2013) believe that this correlation stands for two primary reasons. Firstly, that autocratic governments with broader ‘selectorates’ tend to be more inclined to prioritize public over private benefits. Hypothesis that converges with the argument made by Przeworski (2022) regarding negative assumptions. Consequently, multiparty autocracies, and to a smaller degree single-party ones, will likely favour more liberal trade stances compared to non-party dictatorships, monarchies, and military-led governments, adding another layer for the analysis of these regimes e.g.: party states vs. military juntas.

These distinctions facilitate the conceptualization of authoritarian regimes and their study. Depending on the main area of focus, it is possible to differentiate them avoiding common generalizations from democracy literature. A useful framework can be found in Morgenbesser (2020), which proposes a system that considers the level of sophistication or preference in policy practice of autocracies, using a scale between ‘competitive authoritarian’ and ‘hegemonic authoritarian’. The global trends in growth and trade suggest that competitive authoritarian models are thriving with similar decisions as liberal democracies.

Most countries in Southeast Asia are currently under autocratic rule, with the region having a limited history of liberal democracy. To grasp the nuances of authoritarian governance in Southeast Asia, it is useful to include the political regime continuum. The spectrum begins with liberal democracies, transitions to electoral democracies (like Indonesia and the Philippines), moves to competitive authoritarian regimes (such as Malaysia and Singapore), progresses to

hegemonic authoritarian regimes (including Cambodia and Vietnam), and culminates in closed authoritarian regimes (like Brunei and China). Among them, the countries commonly associated with development, growth, and trade are autocracies. Confirming the notion that not only their economic performance is worth of attention, also the subtle shift in the essence of authoritarianism justifies an improved understanding of its international dynamics and internal processes.

Additionally, the role of authoritarian leaders in policy reform is worth of attention. They are often perceived as the embodiment of party-state leadership, but not all leadership models are sustained in the long-term, some survive for decades while others fall soon after taking power. Gandhi and Przeworski (2007) argue that authoritarian rulers rely on political institutions to contain the threats. Thus, is it possible to infer that the creation of new institutions -by broadening their support basis- extend their tenures. Fitting explanations emerge from how they address increasing inequality through trade openness, as Wu (2015) draws from the Heckscher–Ohlin international trade model and theories on democratic transition, and Bueno de Mesquita and Smith’s (2009) argument that electorates size influences trade policy design. As unskilled workers in authoritarian settings can benefit from international trade, their individual preferences become more amenable to their governments as their country increases their integration in the global economy.

The Case for Vietnam

Vietnam has emerged as the new manufacturing hub of Southeast Asia and the protagonist of the latest iteration of economic delocalization in the Asia Pacific (Figure 11), attracting substantial foreign investment due to its low-cost labour and highly favourable tax conditions.

Figure 11: Stages of economic delocalization in the Asia-Pacific (Abel Gil Lobo, 2017)

While neighbouring countries exercised caution in indirectly safeguarding a significant portion of their industrial and agricultural sectors, Vietnam opted for a more open approach in its pursuit to achieve the levels of development witnessed in Singapore or South Korea. The underlying notion is to speed up offshoring. The allure of low wages attracts foreign investment,

kickstarting a cycle of industrialization and growth that eventually leads companies to seek alternative locations. According to the General Statistics Office of Vietnam (2023), this process takes approximately fifteen years, during which the aim is to train the population to adapt the economy once these companies venture elsewhere—essentially leveraging declining productivity to enhance competitiveness in the future, as seen in the creation of a Provincial Competitiveness Index (2023).

The consistency of authoritarian governance in Vietnam is not as uniform as seen in Singapore. Even though there is a general trend towards a more sophisticated form of authoritarianism (Morgenbesser, 2020), this change is predominantly driven by aspects related to control mechanisms, information systems, and international behaviour (as detailed in Figure 12). Notably, the Vietnamese Communist Party's managed to have economic sanctions removed, fostered relationships with other governing parties, engaged public relations agencies and think tanks based in Washington DC, and run television and radio stations.

Figure 12: Quality of authoritarian rule in Vietnam (Morgenbesser, 2020)

The embrace of international trade and foreign investments has significantly expanded the range of available products in domestic markets. This, coupled with novel income opportunities, has boosted buying power across various social layers, albeit unevenly. The emergence of high-consuming urban middle classes is swift, with Vietnam's middle class recognized as the quickest expanding in Southeast Asia (Hansen, 2017), although economic advancement and modernity underscore increasing disparities and environmental concerns.

At a regional level, Vietnam has progressively engaged with its neighbours through trade and economic interests, along with the shared objective of strengthening multilateral cooperation to counterbalance China's regional influence. Since its accession to ASEAN in 1995, Vietnam has adapted exceptionally well to regional dynamics, its rapid growth and relative assertiveness managing bilateral relations with China, positioning Vietnam as a strong leader in the organization. Their adaptability also positions them as a bridge between the founding members of ASEAN and the second-generation members to which it belongs. Thus serving as platform for Vietnamese integration in an era of inter-regional trade, despite facing uncertainty with the rise of more protectionist policies at a global level. This affirmation is supported by the World Values Survey results measuring regional confidence in ASEAN (Figure 13).

Figure 13: Trust in ASEAN (WVS, 2021)

	TOTAL	ISO 3166-1 numeric country code			
		Indonesia	Singapore	Vietnam	Thailand
A great deal	13.5 (1,066)	15.9	4.3	22.0	13.8
Quite a lot	41.9 (3,318)	41.3	41.4	59.0	30.4
Not very much	24.2 (1,916)	27.3	31.4	7.5	21.4
None at all	5.6 (440)	8.6	3.8	1.8	4.5
Don't know	12.7 (1,001)	6.9	18.8	9.8	19.0
No answer	0.7 (55)	0.0	0.3	-	3.3
Missing: Unknown	1.5 (115)	-	-	-	7.7
(N)	(7,912)	(3,200)	(2,012)	(1,200)	(1,500)

To comprehend Vietnam, it is necessary to examine its Confucian authority structure (Huang, 2022b) that has been constructed as a family-oriented state. Vietnamese were nudged away from exclusively emphasizing familial bonds. Instead, they were prompted to adopt a broader perspective and shift their allegiances towards larger groups, with the nation being the ultimate ideal. Notably, even as the Democratic Republic of Vietnam took steps to break down traditional family structures and promoted more general terms of address, it simultaneously fostered the concept of a state that functions like a family (Pelley, 2002:157-160).

Understanding the Vietnamese State power structure clarifies the nation’s political changes and the potential direction it might take. As depicted in Figure 14, the Party-driven institutional overhaul increased political liberalization. However, it did not facilitate the decentralization of the political power structure. Huang (2022a:166-169) argues that political change in Vietnam could evolve following the Chinese model ‘where revolutions and institutional change brought revolutionary and progressive forces to state domination and authority’ or following the path of the East Asian democracies i.e.: Japan, South Korea, and Taiwan ‘that would see further decentralization and pluralization of the power structure and further institutionalization of new authority relations among influential political forces.’

Figure 14: Power structure and authority relations of the Vietnamese State (Huang, 2022a)

The Vietnamese experience of ‘Developmental Socialism’ maintaining a ‘single-party domination while advancing rapid national development’ (Slater and Wong, 2022:257) has been outshined by the global outreach of China, but it should not be considered a small China at all. Despite sharing the experience of successful Communist Parties leading their national revolution, providing legitimacy to single party rule, geopolitical tensions have increased the

distance between both nations. As a result, the Vietnamese government has increased its engagement with the United States. Should Vietnam persist, reforms promoting openness will be their most effective instrument to demonstrate dedication. If they were to be implemented, their power structure implies that they will most likely be through trade reforms and less likely through democratic institutions. However, is the regional evidence congruent with these approaches? The World Values Survey country comparison tool data presents Vietnam as a *less likely case* when compared with Indonesia, Japan, South Korea, Singapore, and Thailand.

Among East Asian countries Vietnam consistently reports the highest trust scores along with Indonesia and Singapore (Figure 15). Similar results are seen regarding satisfaction with the performance of their country's political system (Figure 16), even though Vietnamese seem to be more satisfied with their political system than citizens from other regional economies.

Figure 15: Trust in Government (WVS, 2021)

	TOTAL	ISO 3166-1 numeric country code					
		Indonesia	Japan	South Korea	Singapore	Vietnam	Thailand
A great deal	22.0 (2,309)	37.1	3.2	4.2	20.9	35.4	12.1
Quite a lot	46.6 (4,894)	41.7	36.7	47.1	59.7	57.5	38.9
Not very much	23.6 (2,482)	17.9	42.0	40.9	15.8	4.2	30.8
None at all	5.1 (533)	2.9	10.1	7.8	2.5	1.0	9.8
Don't know	1.9 (202)	0.4	7.5	-	0.9	1.8	3.2
No answer	0.5 (50)	-	0.6	-	0.2	-	2.5
Other missing; Multiple answers Mail (EVS)	0.4 (39)	-	-	-	-	-	2.6
(N)	(10,510)	(3,200)	(1,353)	(1,245)	(2,012)	(1,200)	(1,500)

Figure 16: Satisfaction with the political system performance (WVS, 2021)

	TOTAL	ISO 3166-1 numeric country code					
		Indonesia	Japan	South Korea	Singapore	Vietnam	Thailand
Not satisfied at all	5.4 (570)	10.9	3.8	0.2	2.1	1.2	7.4
2	2.5 (260)	3.3	3.6	0.1	1.5	0.7	4.3
3	4.6 (481)	5.4	10.0	0.8	2.8	0.8	6.5
4	5.0 (521)	4.9	8.4	1.8	4.1	1.8	8.3
5	14.9 (1,567)	14.9	14.7	6.8	14.3	10.2	26.5
6	14.0 (1,467)	10.9	14.1	24.9	13.9	9.1	15.1
7	20.3 (2,131)	14.8	17.6	41.0	23.8	20.3	12.5
8	16.4 (1,728)	12.5	13.2	21.5	22.8	24.3	8.9
9	5.7 (599)	5.5	3.3	2.3	7.9	10.5	4.4
Completely satisfied	8.9 (930)	14.2	1.6	0.5	5.9	21.2	5.0
Don't know	1.8 (191)	2.6	8.1	-	-	-	-
No answer	0.6 (64)	0.1	1.8	-	1.0	-	1.1
(N)	(10,510)	(3,200)	(1,353)	(1,245)	(2,012)	(1,200)	(1,500)
Mean	6.31	6.05	5.61	6.78	6.70	7.61	5.46
Std Dev.	2.31	2.78	2.11	1.11	1.92	1.89	2.27
Base mean	(10,255)	(3,115)	(1,220)	(1,245)	(1,992)	(1,200)	(1,483)

Across the selected countries, respondents convey strong levels of trust in national press (Figure 17). Although, the Vietnamese population has significant higher level of trust in their national press than its neighbours and regional powerhouses.

Figure 17: Trust in Press (WVS, 2021)

	TOTAL	ISO 3166-1 numeric country code					
		Indonesia	Japan	South Korea	Singapore	Vietnam	Thailand
A great deal	8.7 (919)	13.3	4.7	3.1	6.1	9.6	10.4
Quite a lot	48.1 (5,052)	37.2	64.7	46.4	48.8	69.8	39.3
Not very much	33.9 (3,561)	37.4	24.2	43.5	38.2	15.9	35.8
None at all	7.0 (732)	11.4	3.4	7.0	4.8	3.2	6.6
Don't know	1.6 (170)	0.7	2.7	-	1.9	1.6	3.5
No answer	0.3 (34)	-	0.3	-	0.2	-	1.7
Other missing; Multiple answers Mail (EVS)	0.4 (42)	-	-	-	-	-	2.8
(N)	(10,510)	(3,200)	(1,353)	(1,245)	(2,012)	(1,200)	(1,500)

Interestingly, Vietnam is the highest scorer regarding the importance of democracy in their country (Figure 18) and closely followed by how democratically their country is being governed (Figure 19). As a party-state, Vietnam consistently holds elections, supporting the idea of authoritarian sophistication by Morgenbesser (2020) and validating Przeworski's (2022) call to expand our understanding of this type of regimes.

Figure 18: Importance of democracy (WVS, 2021)

	TOTAL	ISO 3166-1 numeric country code					
		Indonesia	Japan	South Korea	Singapore	Vietnam	Thailand
Not at all important	1.5 (159)	4.2	0.3	-	0.4	0.2	0.7
2	0.6 (62)	1.3	0.2	-	0.2	0.2	0.8
3	0.9 (98)	1.7	0.3	0.6	0.7	0.2	1.0
4	1.2 (129)	1.2	0.4	0.8	1.0	0.3	3.5
5	6.5 (688)	4.3	4.8	6.2	9.5	2.2	12.7
6	6.3 (664)	4.4	3.5	10.2	8.3	2.9	9.8
7	10.5 (1,104)	7.3	7.1	16.9	14.2	10.2	10.4
8	19.1 (2,004)	15.4	18.0	28.5	23.9	18.3	14.2
9	14.3 (1,505)	15.5	12.5	21.6	11.9	12.2	12.3
Absolutely important	36.8 (3,870)	43.4	43.0	15.2	28.2	53.2	33.6
Don't know	1.6 (165)	1.4	6.9	-	1.3	-	-
No answer	0.6 (62)	-	2.9	-	0.3	-	1.1
(N)	(10,510)	(3,200)	(1,353)	(1,245)	(2,012)	(1,200)	(1,500)
Mean	8.22	8.23	8.70	7.90	7.98	8.91	7.83
Std Dev.	2.00	2.39	1.63	1.49	1.80	1.45	2.14
Base mean	(10,282)	(3,155)	(1,220)	(1,245)	(1,979)	(1,200)	(1,483)

Figure 19: How democratically is this country being governed today? (WVS, 2021)

	TOTAL	ISO 3166-1 numeric country code					
		Indonesia	Japan	South Korea	Singapore	Vietnam	Thailand
Not at all democratic	2.4 (254)	3.8	0.7	0.2	1.3	2.0	4.7
2	1.2 (129)	1.3	0.4	0.2	1.2	0.9	3.0
3	2.9 (300)	2.1	3.8	0.6	2.6	0.9	7.2
4	3.3 (351)	3.5	2.8	1.9	3.5	0.9	6.5
5	12.4 (1,301)	10.1	8.6	8.0	14.9	7.8	24.5
6	12.4 (1,299)	8.9	9.3	21.9	14.7	9.2	13.9
7	21.0 (2,204)	17.7	19.0	37.4	24.9	17.8	13.3
8	19.9 (2,096)	17.6	25.4	23.9	22.1	21.2	12.8
9	8.3 (873)	10.0	11.5	5.2	6.2	10.2	5.8
Completely democratic	13.0 (1,371)	21.8	6.6	0.6	6.2	29.0	7.1
Don't know	2.6 (277)	3.1	9.9	-	2.1	-	-
No answer	0.5 (55)	0.1	1.9	-	0.3	-	1.3
(N)	(10,510)	(3,200)	(1,353)	(1,245)	(2,012)	(1,200)	(1,500)
Mean	6.96	7.26	7.13	6.88	6.73	7.81	5.90
Std Dev.	2.10	2.34	1.83	1.19	1.81	2.04	2.27
Base mean	(10,178)	(3,097)	(1,193)	(1,245)	(1,963)	(1,200)	(1,480)

Consequently, Vietnamese trust their political institutions as the party-state government and its leadership, also perceiving the press content as legitimate. If most democratic indexes emphasize elections and freedoms of expression/press, then the Vietnamese ordinary context complies with these indicators that help shape a sophisticated and hegemonic authoritarianism, but what does this mean for trade? Because most Vietnamese emphasize that their country's main priority should be a high level of economic growth (Figure 20, 21).

Figure 20: Aims of country: first choice (WVS, 2021)

	TOTAL	ISO 3166-1 numeric country code					
		Indonesia	Japan	South Korea	Singapore	Vietnam	Thailand
A high level of economic growth	47.6 (5,000)	45.8	43.4	42.2	40.0	52.2	66.0
Making sure this country has strong defence forces	20.3 (2,132)	9.3	14.6	38.4	28.7	24.3	19.3
Seeing that people have more say about how are done at their jobs and in their communities	21.3 (2,244)	29.9	24.3	16.2	25.6	8.3	9.4
Trying to make our cities and countryside more beautiful	9.4 (985)	14.7	10.5	3.1	4.8	15.1	3.7
Don't know	1.0 (102)	0.3	6.8	-	-	-	0.0
No answer	0.4 (47)	0.0	0.4	-	0.9	-	1.6
(N)	(10,510)	(3,200)	(1,353)	(1,245)	(2,012)	(1,200)	(1,500)

Figure 21: Most important first choice (WVS, 2021)

	TOTAL	ISO 3166-1 numeric country code					
		Indonesia	Japan	South Korea	Singapore	Vietnam	Thailand
A stable economy	65.1 (6,846)	74.1	49.2	62.7	62.6	66.2	65.0
Progress toward a less impersonal and more humane society	18.2 (1,912)	10.6	30.5	26.7	21.9	10.3	17.4
Progress toward a society in which Ideas count more than money	6.8 (711)	2.9	3.3	7.6	10.8	10.6	9.0
The fight against crime	9.0 (941)	12.0	12.4	3.0	4.5	12.9	6.9
Don't know	0.4 (44)	0.2	2.7	-	-	-	0.0
No answer	0.3 (31)	0.1	1.9	-	0.1	-	-
Missing: Unknown	0.2 (24)	-	-	-	-	-	1.6
(N)	(10,510)	(3,200)	(1,353)	(1,245)	(2,012)	(1,200)	(1,500)

The Vietnamese growing middle class is aware that their prosperity can only be sustained by economic growth. The media outlets reflect it, and the creation of the Provincial Competitiveness Index provides them with a route map that identifies areas of improvement. Arguably, the PCI could be perceived as means of the central government to maintain its hegemony on provincial politics. This would dovetail with the public discourse embracing free trade and related international organizations like the World Trade Organization (Figure 22) as a remarkable framing of autocratic policy reform based on democratic legitimacy.

Figure 22: Trust in the World Trade Organization (WTO) (WVS, 2021)

	TOTAL	ISO 3166-1 numeric country code					
		Indonesia	Japan	South Korea	Singapore	Vietnam	Thailand
A great deal	13.0 (1,368)	19.8	3.4	7.9	4.8	25.6	12.5
Quite a lot	42.0 (4,411)	46.6	29.1	63.1	38.9	44.2	28.4
Not very much	21.5 (2,256)	23.4	21.1	27.4	28.4	3.5	17.7
None at all	3.6 (379)	5.0	3.6	1.6	3.5	1.0	4.6
Don't know	18.4 (1,934)	5.2	42.1	-	24.0	25.7	27.0
No answer	0.4 (43)	-	0.6	-	0.3	-	1.9
Missing: Unknown	1.1 (119)	-	-	-	-	-	7.9
(N)	(10,510)	(3,200)	(1,353)	(1,245)	(2,012)	(1,200)	(1,500)

The move away from the Soviet economic model might be seen as a step towards globalization. However, the focus should be on the trajectory and outcome of the shift to a market economy. Mainly because it is easy to perceive Vietnamese economic changes as a rapid trade reform approach, akin to shock therapy. Whereas its speed was distant to what happened in the USSR and Hungary in the 1990s. Their model favouring a slower, incremental, and methodical path, kept the state power structure stable and the hegemony of the Communist Party of Vietnam uncontested.

Three decades on, it seems choosing a market economy was a good move. The Vietnamese economic changes show growth, better living standards, and fewer people in poverty. While Eastern European countries reforms covered politics and economics, China and Vietnam only shifted their economy. The Communist Party led a big push to get state-run businesses to stand on their own two feet and face competition. As Sahut and Teulon (2022) describe ‘The institutional infrastructure has been created simultaneously with trade and market liberalisation. All efforts were concentrated on making the market economy emerge in compliance with international standards – legal framework, international practices – as these are the prerequisites for joining the global trade arena.’

However, trade, especially in transitioning economies, carries distribution issues that present troubles to the leadership even in dictatorships. Trade creates winners and losers at a domestic level. Usually, winners benefit from initial trade reforms, accessing a privileged position to tackle future reforms and prosperity. Although to some authors Vietnam can be seen as an outlier handling economic inequality. For example, Malesky (2009) explains that in 1996 Vietnamese reformers found a way out of their unique reform challenges by setting up new provinces. A new voting majority in the Central Committee let them push economic plans that were at odds with the early winners of free trade reforms: the State-Owned Enterprise Sector. Furthermore, the political structures in Vietnam after the reforms offer local leaders’ different incentives. This could explain the variance among regional economic results within Vietnam (PCI), where location and GDP are not directly correlated, but alignment with the central

government seems to influence their overall performance, while the provincial and local power structure alignment seems to be influenced by the public trust in domestic political institutions.

In contrast, a comprehensive study examined the connection between trust and formal structures, assessing bilateral trade trends among 16 EU economies between 1996-2009. Though focused on trade partners institutions, the results show that trust in partners notably boosts bilateral trade. Yet, Yu et. al. (2011) underlines that trust, and formal institutions act as alternatives, ‘as the positive effect of trust on trade is conditional on the quality of formal institutions. When the institutional quality of the importing country increases, the effect of trust on trade decreases, and eventually becomes insignificant.’ This showcases where analytical focus should be as a literature gap. Also, makes the case to measure the probable relation between trust in institutions and engagement in international trade by authoritarian regimes compelling. But how should institutions be approached then?

The most likely answer is to treat the power structure of the Vietnamese party-state as a sole institution separated in its government (as a family hierarchy) and the head of state/government (as a temporary manager of the family’s assets). Pelley (2002:157-160) characterizes the country as a ‘family-state’. To comprehend the country under this concept, it is essential to recognize that the Vietnamese were prompted to broaden their intimate allegiances, ideally towards the nation at large. Notably, during the early years of the DRV steps to break down traditional family structures and more generalized way of addressing one another were promoted. Through these measures, the concept of a united, familial nation was fostered. Thus, the principal institution to analyse for this research is the main family: the central government of the party-state.

Research Design and Method Selection

The main objective of this research is to discern the relationship between trust in domestic political institutions and the implementation of free trade policies by authoritarian regimes. Secondary, to assess if the spread of global trade across developing countries will comprise the diffusion of democratic institutions will maintain its validity as globalization premise, given the increasing autocratic actors engaging in free trade. To that purpose a mixed methods least-likely single case study was chosen, and the Vietnamese process of marketization used as case.

Approach

Why: This study seeks to uncover the causal factors driving authoritarian regimes to adopt free trade without pursuing democratization. It hypothesizes that populations prioritize tangible growth and prosperity from international markets over democratic values, boosting the legitimacy of domestic political institutions in these regimes. Trade matters here because it’s central to international relations, political economy, and development under globalization, while also revealing a country’s openness and economic governance approach.

Limitations and Reflexivity

1. The main limitation is its observational nature that cannot, per se, identify if correlation between social trust and trade preferences in fact reflects a causal effect.
2. This research does not aim to assess the quality or efficiency of regime types. Nor discuss if authoritarian regimes are preferable to democratic ones.
3. Basic command of the Vietnamese language and access to authorities influenced the case selection and research on regards of other cases with similar backgrounds.

4. Time and resource constraints limited the research to a single case study. In ideal conditions the research could be conducted across a selection of Asia-Pacific countries, covering the whole spectrum of economic and democratic transition iterations.

Research Questions

Main research question:

How does trust in domestic political institutions influence the decision-making process of an authoritarian regime to engage with free trade policies?

Secondary research questions:

1. What factors shape trust in domestic political institutions within the context of market opening in the authoritarian regime?
2. What are the implications of trust (or lack thereof) in domestic political institutions for the success and sustainability of free trade policies in the authoritarian regime?
3. How do local newspapers shape public discourse regarding the market opening and delocalization processes in the authoritarian regime?

Variables

Independent variable:

- Engagement in free trade: This variable assesses the extent to which the chosen authoritarian regime actively participates in international trade activities. It encompasses the variance of the regime's involvement in trade agreements, negotiations, and trade policy decisions aimed at promoting international trade relationships.

Dependent variable:

- Trust in domestic political institutions: It represents the level of trust that individuals within a country have in their domestic institutions, such as the government. Considering the structure of the Vietnamese 'family-state' it was separated into 'trust in government' and 'trust in head of state'.

Control variable:

- Trust in press: It represents the degree of confidence individuals have in the accuracy, reliability, and impartiality of information and news provided by media sources. It reflects the level of belief in the credibility of media outlets and their reporting.

Research Design

This work implements least-likely single case study to analyse Vietnam; limited scope process tracing -particularly historical institutionalism- to identify critical junctures since 1990 to the present day; regression analysis accompanied with Levene test within datasets; and discourse analysis to operationalize the identified critical junctures.

The consulted methods literature includes Berg-Schlosser (2012), Gerring (2022), and Ragin (2008) as a general starting point for mixed methods. Regarding least-likely single case study Koivu et. al. (2017), Gerring (2004), and Willis (2014) were consulted. Ricks and Liu (2018)

and Yan (2023) provided solid groundworks for the inclusion of process tracing in the qualitative component, complemented with the blog of *ingorholving* (2016) favouring process tracing as a companion for least-likely case studies. De Percy (2020) justifies the use of historical institutionalism -within process tracing- to identify critical junctures, as it eases the operationalization of findings with quantitative data analysis results and facilitates contextualization to implement discourse analysis. Regarding discourse analysis and media framing, basic understanding and framework were consulted in Matthes and Kohring (2008), and Semetko and Valkenburg (2000). Framing analysis regarding trade and policy issues were conducted influenced by the work of Gravelle (2020). Lastly, counterfactuals (Annex 1) were consulted in the work of Ragin (2008:160-175).

Data Collection

A combination of quantitative and qualitative data was collected. Quantitative data was obtained through the Asian Barometer and World Values Survey (WVS) datasets. Qualitative data was gathered through the analysis of the five main Vietnamese media outlets (Annex 2) and the US Department of Commerce compilation of trade agreements signed by Vietnam.

Data Analysis Methods

Regression analysis, Levene's test, and Discourse Analysis.

Findings

Quantitative Data Analysis

Quantitative data analysis was conducted with Stata 17 Standard Edition.

World Values Survey Results

The first analysis explored how trust in government relates to trade (Figure 23). The results show a positive link: as trust in government rises, free trade engagement grows too. The coefficient's size suggests this connection is strong. With a p-value below 0.05, the finding holds statistical weight, meaning it is unlikely just random noise. However, the R-squared value indicates a decent but not perfect fit—trust in government explains some of trade's ups and downs, though not overwhelmingly.

Figure 23: Regression result Trade and Trust in Government WVS

Source	SS	df	MS	Number of obs	=	93,831
				F(1, 93829)	=	1809.49
Model	2.6942e+10	1	2.6942e+10	Prob > F	=	0.0000
Residual	1.3970e+12	93,829	14889027.3	R-squared	=	0.0189
				Adj R-squared	=	0.0189
Total	1.4240e+12	93,830	15176000.2	Root MSE	=	3858.6
Trade	Coefficient	Std. err.	t	P> t	[95% conf. interval]	
Trust_Govmt	395.1984	9.290455	42.54	0.000	376.9892	413.4076
_cons	-2725.953	26.20839	-104.01	0.000	-2777.321	-2674.585

With a p-value less than 0.05 the result is statistically significant, indicating that the relationship is likely not due to chance. Likewise, the R-squared value in the regression output represents a good but not significant fit. Showing that trust in government could explain but not by robust means the variations in trade.

Interestingly, while measuring by trust in head of state (Figure 24), the results are negative. Highlighting the relevance of data context. WVS 7th wave was conducted in 2021, the year that Vietnamese growth plummeted for the first time in decades, and public opinion revealed poor crisis management by the administration.

Figure 24: Regression result Trade and Trust in Head of State WVS

Source	SS	df	MS	Number of obs	=	93,831
Model	1.3657e+10	1	1.3657e+10	F(1, 93829)	=	908.64
Residual	1.4103e+12	93,829	15030605.9	Prob > F	=	0.0000
				R-squared	=	0.0096
				Adj R-squared	=	0.0096
Total	1.4240e+12	93,830	15176000.2	Root MSE	=	3876.9

Trade	Coefficient	Std. err.	t	P> t	[95% conf. interval]
Trust_Head_of_State	-115.9766	3.84747	-30.14	0.000	-123.5176 -108.4356
_cons	-2075.967	16.68345	-124.43	0.000	-2108.666 -2043.267

The R-squared value again shows that there is not a strong fit between both variables. It is expectable that the handling of the COVID19 pandemic influenced the answers.

When controlled by trust in press, results show similar patterns. As trust in press increases, the trust in government tends to increase (Figure 25). Whereas the opposite can be seen while measured against trust in the head of state (Figure 26). A likely explanation is that issue framing in media outlets is influenced by context, but overall, the power structure keeps respected.

Figure 25: Regression result Trust in Government and Trust in Press WVS

Source	SS	df	MS	Number of obs	=	94,278
Model	17348.0415	1	17348.0415	F(1, 94276)	=	10504.44
Residual	155696.447	94,276	1.65149611	Prob > F	=	0.0000
				R-squared	=	0.1003
				Adj R-squared	=	0.1002
Total	173044.489	94,277	1.83548998	Root MSE	=	1.2851

Trust_Govmt	Coefficient	Std. err.	t	P> t	[95% conf. interval]
Trust_Press	.4020033	.0039223	102.49	0.000	.3943155 .409691
_cons	1.419032	.0111364	127.42	0.000	1.397205 1.440859

Figure 26: Regression result Trust in Head of State and Trust in Press WVS

Source	SS	df	MS	Number of obs	=	94,278
Model	1371.61398	1	1371.61398	F(1, 94276)	=	127.45
Residual	1014616.57	94,276	10.7621937	Prob > F	=	0.0000
				R-squared	=	0.0014
				Adj R-squared	=	0.0013
Total	1015988.19	94,277	10.7766283	Root MSE	=	3.2806

Trust_Head-e	Coefficient	Std. err.	t	P> t	[95% conf. interval]
Trust_Press	-.1130369	.0100128	-11.29	0.000	-.1326619 -.093412
_cons	-2.533303	.0284287	-89.11	0.000	-2.589023 -2.477583

Asian Barometer Results

The Asian Barometer does not specifically include trade, but a small set of socio-economic questions that relate to trade were analysed. The results show a significant relation in the satisfaction with their current financial situation, how better is their economic situation compared to their parents, and how democratic is the country when measured against trust in government (Figure 27) and trust in the head of state (Figure 28). Although in both cases the p-value shows that the relation is statistically insignificant to assess the comparison influence between respondent's and their parents' situation.

Figure 27: Regression result Trust in Government Asian Barometer

Source	SS	df	MS	Number of obs	=	1,200
Model	30843.2828	3	10281.0943	F(3, 1196)	=	32.84
Residual	374455.75	1,196	313.090092	Prob > F	=	0.0000
				R-squared	=	0.0761
				Adj R-squared	=	0.0738
Total	405299.032	1,199	338.030886	Root MSE	=	17.694

	Trust_Govmt	Coefficient	Std. err.	t	P> t	[95% conf. interval]
Satisfaction_financial_situation		3.668217	.6612149	5.55	0.000	2.370947 4.965487
Situation_compared_parents		.1957085	.6652746	0.29	0.769	-1.109527 1.500944
How_Democratic		2.21692	.332333	6.67	0.000	1.5649 2.868941
_cons		-9.153928	2.041559	-4.48	0.000	-13.15936 -5.148492

Figure 28: Regression result Trust in Head of State Asian Barometer

Source	SS	df	MS	Number of obs	=	1,200
Model	23768.6262	3	7922.87539	F(3, 1196)	=	30.88
Residual	306818.853	1,196	256.537503	Prob > F	=	0.0000
				R-squared	=	0.0719
				Adj R-squared	=	0.0696
Total	330587.479	1,199	275.719332	Root MSE	=	16.017

	Trust_Head_of_State	Coefficient	Std. err.	t	P> t	[95% conf. interval]
Satisfaction_financial_situation		3.139598	.5985265	5.25	0.000	1.965319 4.313877
Situation_compared_parents		.1813595	.6022013	0.30	0.763	-1.000129 1.362848
How_Democratic		1.982294	.3008252	6.59	0.000	1.39209 2.572498
_cons		-7.998751	1.848003	-4.33	0.000	-11.62444 -4.373062

Levene's Test Results

Both datasets include trust in the head of state and trust in the national government as variables. The Levene test output identifies values higher than 0.05 (Figure 29), denoting that there is no significance variance between the trust scores on both datasets.

Figure 29: Levene test results for Trust in Head of State and Trust in Government comparing WVS and Asian Barometer

source	Summary of 7 Trust in the executive office (president or prime minister)			source	Summary of 9 National government in the capital city		
	Mean	Std. dev.	Freq.		Mean	Std. dev.	Freq.
2	5.2541667	16.604798	1,200	2	6.0575	18.385616	1,200
Total	5.2541667	16.604798	1,200	Total	6.0575	18.385616	1,200

W0 = .	df(0, 1199)	Pr > F = .	W0 = .	df(0, 1199)	Pr > F = .
W50 = .	df(0, 1199)	Pr > F = .	W50 = .	df(0, 1199)	Pr > F = .
W10 = .	df(0, 1199)	Pr > F = .	W10 = .	df(0, 1199)	Pr > F = .

Qualitative data analysis

Policy framing is a popular field of study that includes foreign policy. This research considered the domain of trade policy attitudes (Gravelle, 2020). It makes plausible that highlighting the economic significance of international trade relationships for one's nation can increase preferences towards tighter trade connections. And, if individuals perceive potential economic advantages by personal gains or national benefits, they should be more likely to endorse trade policies.

A manual holistic approach (Matthes and Kohring, 2008) was conducted, adapting the economic consequences frame explained in Semetko and Valkenburg (2000). Time constraints limited the implementation of more sophisticated analysis or the inclusion of digital tools.

Economic Consequences Frames Concepts

A set of preliminary concepts framing economic consequences was selected (impact of trade in the nation, population, and national government) to validate their relevance in relation to the sources before analysis, as Vietnamese media and official documents tend to publish following specific editorial structures and language forms. As a result, the following list of feasible concepts was compiled (Figure 30).

Figure 30: Issue specific frames for trade policy reform in Vietnamese media

English	Trade	Policy	Reform	Governance	Economic Growth
Vietnamese	Thương mại	Chính sách	Cải cách	Quản trị	Tăng trưởng kinh tế
English	National Interest	Political Leadership	International Relations	Strategic Partnership	Sovereignty
Vietnamese	Lợi ích quốc gia	Lãnh đạo chính trị	Quan hệ quốc tế	Đối tác chiến lược	Chủ quyền
English	Development	Public Perception	Market Access	Diplomacy	Globalization
Vietnamese	Phát triển	Quan điểm của công chúng	Tiếp cận thị trường	Ngoại giao	Toàn cầu hóa

Identified Critical Junctures

The initial aim was to validate binary compliance (yes/no) of the concept list and reduce the number of sources to review, through reiteration, and identify the most relevant critical junctures (Figure 31). Later, list of critical junctures was contrasted with the selected publications to interpret framing and juncture presentation on media outlets (Figure 32). Unexpectedly, some outlets did not keep extensive repositories, while some did not exist during the first two or three junctures, limiting results.

Figure 31: Identified critical junctures for trade in Vietnam since 1990

Episode	Critical Juncture	Causal Mechanism
1990 - 1995 Doi Moi Reforms	Introduction of the Doi Moi Reforms in 1986, leading to a transition from a centrally planned economy to a socialist-oriented market economy.	The failure of the centralized economy, international pressure, and the desire for economic growth.
1995 - 2000 International Integration	Vietnam's accession to ASEAN in 1995.	The need for regional economic integration and access to new markets.
2000 - 2007 Bilateral Trade Agreements	The signing of the Bilateral Trade Agreement (BTA) with the United States in 2000.	The desire to attract foreign investment and boost exports.
2007 - 2015 WTO Accession and Further Liberalization	Vietnam's accession to the WTO in 2007.	The need to integrate further into the global economy and pressure from international organizations.
2015 - Present Comprehensive Economic Partnerships	Signing of the Comprehensive and Progressive Agreement for Trans-Pacific Partnership (CPTPP) in 2018.	The desire to diversify trade partners and align with international standards.

Figure 32: Media frames on trade reforms in Vietnam since 1990

Episode	Presentation
1990 - 1995 Doi Moi Reforms	Emphasizing the need for modernization and economic growth, the government framed the reforms as a necessary step towards prosperity. The language focused on self-reliance, innovation, and alignment with global economic practices.
1995 - 2000 International Integration	Joining ASEAN was framed as a strategic move to enhance regional cooperation and solidarity. The government emphasized the benefits of regional integration, such as increased trade opportunities and collaboration on shared challenges.
2000 - 2007 Bilateral Trade Agreements	The BTA with the US was presented as a landmark achievement, symbolizing Vietnam's growing international stature. The government highlighted the potential for increased investment, job creation, and technological advancement.
2007 - 2015 WTO Accession and Further Liberalization	Accession to the WTO was framed as a significant milestone in Vietnam's integration into the global economy. The government emphasized the alignment with international standards, commitment to fair trade practices, and potential for economic growth.
2015 - Present Comprehensive Economic Partnerships	The signing of agreements like the CPTPP was portrayed as a strategic move to diversify trade partners and enhance Vietnam's position in the global trade network. The government focused on the potential benefits for various sectors of the economy and the alignment with broader development goals.

Discussion

These findings confirm Southeast Asia's value for global studies. The region's dynamism makes it a rich field for many disciplines, though not without hurdles. This study needed multiple tools to get the job done, and mixing methods proved the right call. In terms of theory, the English School of International Relations worked well—it streamlined the practical analysis of globalization, which depends on the meaning leaders give it.

Accordingly, it seems that Vietnamese leaders frame critical junctures in national media in ways that support their agenda. This behaviour has proven particularly effective to maintain the party-state hegemonic condition while implementing marketization reforms and conducting

elections at all levels. In other words, trade is a valuable resource to Vietnamese policy makers to politicize and securitize their agenda at domestic and international scenarios. Evidence also suggests that the Vietnamese population keeps higher expectations on their national government. Although potential disappointments on their performance or service delivery are openly manifested in media outlets, they are usually presented as contestation to local or provincial officials on contrast to national officials e.g.: National Assembly, are perceived as the final appeal instance to solve their grudges.

Conclusion

The findings revalidate the importance of Southeast Asia for global studies. The region dynamism makes it an interesting source of inquiry for diverse disciplines, interest that is not without challenges. To complete this research the use of more than one disciplinary toolset was required and mixed methods consistently proved to be the appropriate choice. From the perspective of scholarly theory, the English School of International Relations responded efficiently as it helped to simplify the operationalization that practice-centred globalization analysis requires, as it does not exist independently of the meaning imputed by policymakers.

Despite the congruence between the hypothesis and the findings, the research lacked more robust findings to extrapolate causality, ideally with datasets that matched the dates of the identified critical junctures. Also, the research design prioritised feasibility than complexity. Future exercises will require adjustments to grasp the whole spectrum of democratization and globalization in the most dynamic region in the world. It will be interesting to extend the research into other countries in the region and regional organizations like APEC and ASEAN. Nevertheless, the unique interplay of trade policy within authoritarian settings might constrain the broad applicability of these observations to other policy domains.

Finally, despite the limited findings, it is possible to assert that the inclination of autocratic governments to adopt free trade challenges the premise of democracy's spread through trade on a global scale, indicating that among authoritarian regimes markets likely substitute democracy. The ongoing trend of increasing authoritarianism across the globe is solid evidence of this and will probably persist in impacting autocratic leaders' eagerness to remain in power using international commerce as another tool at their disposal. It reminds us of the necessity to improve our understanding of these regimes as potential main trade partners.

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Appendices

Appendix 1: Ranking of Vietnamese media outlets by popularity

Figure 33: Ranking of Vietnamese media outlets by popularity

Rank	Outlet	Website	Category
1	Vietnam Express	vnexpress.net	News & Media Publishers
2	Zing News	zingnews.vn	News & Media Publishers
3	24 Gia	24h.com.vn	News & Media Publishers
4	Dan Tri	dantri.com.vn	News & Media Publishers
5	Tuoi Tre	tuoitre.vn	News & Media Publishers

Source: <https://www.similarweb.com/top-websites/vietnam/news-and-media/>

Appendix 2: Selected questions from WVS and Asian Barometer

Figure 34: Selected questions from World Values Survey and Asian Barometer

WVS question	Description
Q50	Satisfaction with financial situation of household
Q56	Standard of living comparing with your parents
Q66	Confidence: The Press
Q71	Confidence: The Government
Q82_ASEAN	Confidence: The Association of South East Asian Nations (ASEAN)
Q89	Confidence: The World Trade Organization (WTO)
Q152	Aims of country: first choice
Q156	Most important: first choice
Q250	Importance of democracy
Q251	How democratically is this country being governed today
Q293	How much you trust [name of the Head of State]
Trade	Trade (% of GDP) [World Bank, 2019]

Asian Barometer question	Description
Q1	How would you rate the overall economic condition of our country today
Q5	How would you compare the current economic condition of your family with that
Q7	Trust in the executive office (president or prime minister)
Q9	National government in the capital city
Q100	In your opinion how much of a democracy is our country?

Note: misspellings are included in the original dataset